

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH A COMMON MEANING “HOSPITALITY”

¹Najmiddinova Mehriqul Najmiddin qizi, ²Furqatova Hokima Akobir qizi, ³Nabiyeva Dilso‘z G‘iyosiddin qizi,

¹Navoiy davlat universiteti o‘qituvchisi, ^{2,3}Navoiy davlat universiteti talabasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259715>

Abstract. *The phraseological unit “hospitality” is one of the important cultural and linguistic aspects of the Uzbek language. This unity is associated not only linguistically, but also with cultural, ethnographic and sociological aspects. The word “hospitality” is an expression in Uzbek and English that expresses respect and reverence for visitors, has been studied, appreciated in culture, and is part of a way of life.*

Keywords: value, hospitality, culture, speech, pragmatics, linguoculturology, oral speech, neutral, politeness.

Аннотация. *Фразеологическая единица “гостеприимство” является одним из важных культурных и лингвистических аспектов узбекского языка. Это единство связано не только с лингвистическими, но и с культурными, этнографическими и социологическими аспектами. Слово “гостеприимство” - это выражение в узбекском и английском языках, которое выражает уважение и почтение к посетителям, изучается, ценится в культуре и является частью образа жизни.*

Ключевые слова: ценность, гостеприимство, культура, речь, прагматика, лингвокультурология, устная речь, нейтралитет, вежливость.

Annotatsiya. *“Mehmondo‘stlik” frazeologik birligi o‘zbek tilining muhim madaniy va lingvistik jihatlaridan biridir. Bu birlik nafaqat lingvistik, balki madaniy, etnografik va sotsiologik jihatlar bilan ham bog‘liq. “Mehmondo‘stlik” so‘zi o‘zbek va ingliz tillarida mehmonlarga bo‘lgan hurmat va ehtiromni ifoda etuvchi, madaniyatda o‘rganilgan, qadrlangan va hayot tarzining bir qismidir.*

Kalit so‘zlar: qadriyat, mehmondo‘stlik, madaniyat, nutq, pragmatika, lingvokulturologiya, og‘zaki nutq, neytral, xushmuomalalik.

The phraseological unity of “hospitality” is one of the linguistic features of the Uzbek language and is important in the social relations, culture and way of life of the Uzbek people. This phrase is used not only as a combination of words, but also as an element that expresses echoes in the interactions of language and culture. The linguistic features of “hospitality” can be covered through the following aspects:

Lexical-semantic features.

The phraseological unit “hospitality” concentrates two main components in itself in English:

- A guest is a stranger, usually someone who has been a guest. All ritual and traditional treats, associated with the guest's entry into the House, are associated with spiritual values.
- Friendship is a social bond based on sincere, open and respect, where the term friendship means living, supporting and respecting together.

Together, these two words reflect the politeness, sincerity and respect for the guests of the Uzbek people. This approach contributes to the development of a significant and friendly relationship in culture with respect to human interaction.

The word “hospitality” combines the concepts of “guest” and “friendship” in Uzbek. The compound has two main meanings:

Politeness and sincerity to guests: waiting for a guest, treating him with caution and ensuring his comfort is, of course, one of the main values of the Uzbek people.

Culture of treatment and etiquette in society: Hospitality also shows sincerity, respect and trust in interactions. It corresponds to the ancient traditions of the Uzbek people and is one of the main rules of the people in social communication.

Hospitality and Uzbek national culture: the politeness of the Uzbek people to guests and their appreciation have their historical and cultural roots. In many regions of Uzbekistan, hospitality values are extremely important to the people. For example, the old Uzbeks waited for the guest not only with food, but also with their best things.

Language and national spirit: the phraseological unity of “hospitality” demonstrates the sincerity and openness of the Uzbek language. In the language of the Uzbek people there are many proverbs, idioms and phrases that express a good attitude towards guests. For example: expressions such as “*The guest is expected to glorify myself*”, “*Head to the guest and wish to the king*”, “*If the guest comes, let me show your face*” mean a high appreciation of hospitality.

Etymology and historical context.

Historical views: hospitality stems from the centuries-old historical traditions and lifestyle of the people. Since the Uzbeks lived a nomadic lifestyle in many ancient times, the expectation of a visitor was of great importance in their culture. This, on the one hand, is more pronounced in the rural areas of the country, and on the other, it is associated with the development of hotel culture in the cities.

Cultural codes and hospitality.

Cultural codes: Hospitality is an integral part of social interaction in many peoples, including the Uzbek people, especially in rural and small communities. The codex contains teachings such as “*The Sultan in the guest house*”, “*Show the soup if the guest comes*”. There are also artistic and philosophical aspects of waiting for guests and treating them with caution.

Appreciation of hospitality: in the language of the Uzbek people, the term “hospitality” represents the nature and culture of many peoples. Waiting for a guest is seen as a symbol of interaction and people's hard work and kindness.

In general, the phraseological unity of “*hospitality*” is an important element in the language, social and cultural relations of the Uzbek people. This expression reflects the respect, values, traditional culture and social relations of the Uzbek people to visitors. Hospitality is also highly valued in other peoples, but in Uzbeks these traditions form deeper, more vital aspects.

REFERENCES

1. **Azimov I.** “Hospitality in Uzbek Linguistics and Culture”.2013.
2. **Yuldashev F.H.** “Эътиқод” лингвомаънавиятшунослик луғати.–Navoiy.2021.-70 б.
3. **Qayumova M.S.** Syntactic analysis of category of negation in Uzbek and English language. Candidate of philology of science.dissertation. – Tashkent.2010.
4. **Najmiddinova M.N. Najmiddinova S.N. Baxtiyorova G.R. Otanazarova M.M.** “Models of terminological sign” International multidisciplinary journal for research & development ISSN 2394-6334, <https://www.ijmrd.in/index.php/imjrd>, Volume 10, Issue 11. 2023.
5. **Holmes J.** “Women, Men and Politeness”. 1995.
6. **Khodjaev N.** “Hospitality in Uzbek Culture: Linguistic and Cultural Insights”. Tashkent State University Press. 2020.

7. **Najmiddinova M.N.** “Differences between L1 and L2 learning”, VITAL ANNEX: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF NOVEL RESEARCH IN ADVANCED SCIENCES. Impact Factor: 9.5. Germany. 2022.
8. **Nazaryan R.** “The Uzbek Concept of Hospitality and Its Social Implications”. Tashkent University Press. 2015.
9. **АРНОЛЬД И. В.** “Лексикология современного английского языка “Москва “Высшая школа”. 1986.
10. **Kayumova M.S., F.A.Sobirova., M.N.Najmiddinova.** “Specific features of the category of negation in the english language ” EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD) Volume: 5| Issue:3 |, March 2020.
11. **Najmiddinova M.N.** “The similarities and differences between first language and second language acquisition”, AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL AND HUMANITARIAN RESEARCH. Impact Factor: 7.543, ISSN: 2690-9626(Online) America. 2022.
12. **Najmiddinova M.N., Hotamova I.I., Najmiddinova G. N.** “Comparative study of terms related to techniques representing negativity” International journal of scientific researchers, www.wordlyknowledge.uz, Volume:2, Issue:1. 2023.
13. **Shuhrat Yuldashev.** “Uzbek Traditions of Hospitality: A Linguistic Perspective”. 2017.
14. **Smith J.** “Hospitality in English and American Cultures”. Oxford University Press. 2013.
15. **Wierzbicka A.** “Cross-Cultural Pragmatics: The Semantics of Human Interaction”. Walter de Gruyter. 2003.
16. **Rahimov T.** “Proverbs and the Uzbek Identity”. 2015.